

PARTHENOS

Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

Second Year Communication Report, and Updated Communication Plan

KNAW-NIOD, PIN, FHP

28 July 2017

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the work of PARTHENOS WP8 “Communication, dissemination and outreach” during the second year of the project (May 2016-April 2017). It is an updated version of the PARTHENOS Deliverable D8.2 *Initial Communication Plan* that was produced in July 2015, and that was revised in July 2016 in *D8.3 First Year Communication Report, and Updated Communication Plan*. Whereas the *Initial Communication Plan* presented an overall dissemination and communication strategy, and provided a detailed plan of relevant activities for the project’s first year, *The First Year Communication Report* reported on the implementation of the *Initial Communication Plan* during the project’s first twelve months, proposed minor corrections to the overall strategy, and set out our plans for year two. The present deliverable evaluates our communication activities up until the end of year two, and proposes a plan of action for year three. Throughout the project, we will continue to co-ordinate and evaluate the implementation of our communication and dissemination strategy and update reports will be prepared in months 39 and 48 of the project.

The general objectives of PARTHENOS WP8 are to:

- disseminate effectively the project goals and outcomes;
- set up efficient tools for the communication towards various stakeholders (scientific communities, professionals, decisions makers, public, etc.);
- exploit synergies in liaisons and collaborations.

The present document demonstrates that we have made good progress towards meeting our objectives. In particular, the document presents an overall assessment of the success of our existing communication and dissemination strategy, including necessary revisions (section 3); reports in detail on all relevant dissemination and communication tasks in the second year (section 4); provides a quantitative assessment of our activities against the evaluation criteria set in the *First Year Communication Report* (section 5); and finally outlines our detailed plans for the next twelve months (section 6) and establishes revised evaluation criteria for this period (section 7).

2 Introduction

The PARTHENOS project is premised upon a collaboration of sixteen partners from nine European countries, comprising the two European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) active in the broad fields of the humanities – DARIAH and CLARIN – as well as institutions active in European research infrastructure projects – ARIADNE, CENDARI, CHARISMA/IPERION-CH, EHRI, DCH-RP. Marshalling such a comprehensive consortium, the PARTHENOS projects aims to:

- increase the cohesion of research in the fields of Language Studies, Digital Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology and related fields;
- define and implement common guidelines and best practices enabling cross-discipline data curation policies;
- establish a vision about shared virtual research methods for humanities supported by foresight studies;
- mainstream standardization and interoperability in order to support data sharing and re-use;
- develop common tools for data oriented services.

All these high-level aims are critically dependent upon successful collaboration between disparate infrastructures to increase their cohesion, inter-disciplinarily and inter-operability. Therefore, a coordinated and comprehensive approach to dissemination and communication is crucial for the project to achieve its aims and to maximise its impact.

Work package (WP) 8 is charged with planning, coordinating and implementing all of the project's communication and dissemination activities. In month three of the project, it delivered a comprehensive *Initial Communication Plan*¹ that:

- set out PARTHENOS' overall communication and dissemination strategy;

¹ See Reto Speck et al. "D8.2 Initial Communication Plan", *PARTHENOS Deliverable*, July 2015 available at http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/Deliverables/D8.2_Initial_Communication_Plan.pdf.

- identified the project's stakeholder communities;
- presented a set of core communication messages;
- analysed the communication resources available to the project;
- described the project's own communication channels and dissemination materials that are to be produced by the project;
- listed external dissemination opportunities;
- and set evaluation targets for the first twelve months.

This plan was revised and expanded in deliverable *First Year Communication Report*², submitted in M15.

The present document reports on the implementation of the revised plan during the second year of the project (May 2016-April 2017) and contains the planning of communication and dissemination activities for the third year (May 2017-April 2018). It presents an overall assessment of the success of our existing communication and dissemination strategy, including necessary revisions (section 3); reports in detail on all relevant dissemination and communication tasks in the second year (section 4); provides a quantitative assessment of our activities against the evaluation criteria set in the *First Year Communication Report* (section 5); and finally outlines our detailed plans for the next twelve months (section 6) and establishes revised evaluation criteria for this period (section 7).

² See Reto Speck et al. "D8.3 *First Year Communication Report, and Updated Communication Plan*", PARTHENOS Deliverable, July 2016 available at http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/Deliverables/D8.3-First_year_communication_report_and_updated_plan.pdf.

3 Revisions to communication and dissemination strategy

The overall communication and dissemination strategy outlined in sections 3-6 of the *Initial Communication Plan* and revised in section 3 of the *First Year Communication Report* has served the project well so far. As will be shown in more detail in section 5 below, following this strategy has enabled us to reach, and even exceed, most of the targets set for the first twenty four months.

In this section we will recapitulate in brief the main elements of our overall strategy - objectives, high-level communication and dissemination principles, stakeholder groups and tailored messages – and indicate, where relevant, necessary adjustments and revisions to the initial strategy.

3.1 Overall objectives

The PARTHENOS Description of Action defines three overall objectives for the project's communication and dissemination activities:

1. to disseminate effectively the project goals and outcomes;
2. to set up efficient tools for the communication towards various stakeholders (scientific communities, professionals, decisions makers, public, etc.)
3. to exploit synergies in liaisons and collaborations.

In order to achieve these general objectives, the *Initial Communication Plan* defines five specific objectives:

1. to identify and involve internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
2. to create an affiliate network of external stakeholders (research infrastructures and networks in related fields);
3. to ensure that PARTHENOS reaches the core scientific communities in language studies, digital humanities, digital heritage, archaeology and history, as well as professionals in related fields;

4. to raise awareness about PARTHENOS amongst policy makers, funding bodies and major related public institutions;
5. to devise a strategy to involve the general public and attract non-professional audiences.

We believe that both the general and specific objectives remain valid for our work, and that no major revisions are required.

As will become clear throughout this report, we have made good progress towards reaching all these objectives. Nevertheless, we recognise that we will need to step-up our dissemination activities in the forthcoming period, if PARTHENOS is to attain the level of visibility among all relevant stakeholder groups that it deserves. With an increasing amount of substantive research results and products progressively becoming available, we are confident that we will be able to significantly raise the project's profile via dissemination and communication activities. Thereby we will also address a key recommendation resulting from PARTHENOS' recent mid-term review, namely that the project should ensure that its significant achievements are as well and widely known as is possible.

3.2 Communication and dissemination principles

The *Initial Communication Plan* specifies five core communication and dissemination principles that should inform our activities:

1. **Adaptability.** Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication strategy needs to be comprehensive enough to cover the project as a whole, while being adaptable to the project's various research themes and stakeholder communities. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach particular target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users.
2. **Flexibility.** As per the previous pillar, PARTHENOS' communication needs to be flexible and open, in order to create a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.
3. **Dynamism.** The dynamic element is the natural consequence of the two points above. A dynamic strategy is a key to maximise the impact of PARTHENOS.

4. **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.** As stated above, PARTHENOS needs to be able to speak to academic audiences in a variety of fields, as well as to decision makers and the public at large. To achieve this, PARTHENOS will follow a multi-layered communication strategy that formulates core messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication).
5. **Exploitation of synergies:** PARTHENOS is a clustering project across existing Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives and e-infrastructures in the fields of Digital Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Language Studies³, Archaeology and related fields. As such, the project can draw upon a plethora of expertise, networks and dissemination and communication channels that are already in existence at partner institutions and related projects and that can reach the specific subject communities with which PARTHENOS wishes to engage. PARTHENOS needs to exploit to the fullest the synergy that can be achieved by building bridges between these existing resources, and must avoid a duplication of effort. Therefore, achieving better co-ordination and cross-fertilisation of existing communication and dissemination activities is central to PARTHENOS' mission.

As with the objectives, these principles have proven their use and do not need a major update for the project's third year. As anticipated in the *First Year Communication Report*, we have over the last twelve months particularly focused on fully implementing the "exploitation of synergies" principle, not least through PARTHENOS' involvement in Communications Collaboration between European Research Infrastructures initiative (see <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/research-infrastructures-news/>).

3.3 Stakeholder groups

The *Initial Communication Plan* identifies and analyses a set of stakeholder communities, and classifies these into three groups according to the influence and mutual dependence that exist between these communities and PARTHENOS. Figure 1 below provides a visual representation of our initial stakeholder analysis:

³ In the *Initial Communication Plan* we referred to "Linguistic Studies" rather than "Language Studies". We have since adopted the terminology for the reasons explained in section 3.4 below.

¹ Research Infrastructures

² Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums

Figure 1: Stakeholder map

During the project's first 24 months, we have not identified any additional stakeholder communities which merit inclusion in our stakeholder map, nor have we detected any major problems with our detailed stakeholder analysis.

However, in the course of the PARTHENOS mid-term review two nuanced suggestions were made in regard to the researcher stakeholder group:

- PARTHENOS should be more open towards Central and Eastern Europe, and involve institutions and/or individual researchers from those countries.

- PARTHENOS should pay particular attention on how young researchers will benefit from the products it develops.

We are in full agreement with both suggestions, and we will formulate and implement a plan on how we can better reach those two sub stakeholder groups. In regard to engaging young researchers, we are planning to extend our social media presence, and we are further hoping to devise specific activities that are particularly geared towards younger researchers' needs and interests. In regard to our reach in Central and Eastern Europe, we are currently mapping PARTHENOS' partners existing relationships to institutions and individuals in those regions as a first step towards increasing our geographical reach across Europe.

In terms of our general strategy towards engaging stakeholder communities, the focus during the first twelve month was in the first instance on “direct” stakeholders – partners and affiliated Research Infrastructures. During the last year we have extended our activities geared towards reaching “close” stakeholder. The priority for the forthcoming period is to maintain and strengthen our existing relationship with “direct” and “close” stakeholders and to successively reach out to “societal” stakeholder communities.

3.4 Tailored messages

The *Initial Communication Plan* defines five messages tailored towards the achievement of particular communication goals and towards particular stakeholder groups. These messages are:

- General message
- Extended general message
- Research and educational message
- Jargon-free public message
- Policy- and decision-maker message

These messages have successfully informed our communication and dissemination activities during the first two periods, and do not any significant revisions.

However, the PARTHENOS mid-term review resulted in a general recommendation for the project to distinguish more clearly between the achievements and results emanating directly from the project, and the ones that are the results of the ongoing work in the contributing infrastructures, and particularly DARIAH and CLARIN.

We believe that as far as the project's communication and dissemination work is concerned this division is, to a considerable extent, already in place – for instance in the clear separation between Project News and Partners' news on the PARTHENOS website. At the same time, we recognise that the exact positioning of PARTHENOS as a meta-infrastructure is still work-in-progress. We plan to particularly focus on clarifying the relationship between PARTHENOS and the contributing RIs, for instance by publishing a series of short videos that will concisely explain this relationship from a variety of perspectives, and by focusing on the interaction between PARTHENOS and the contributing RIs when we update our publicity materials (see section 6.4 below for details).

4 Report on activities during first year

This section provides short narrative reports on the major activities undertaken in WP8 for the period May 2016 to April 2017. A summary assessment of these activities against the targets set in the *First Year Communication Report* is provided in section 5 below.

4.1 Website

The project website – available via <http://www.parthenos-project.eu> – is one of our main dissemination channels. It is a hub for all the information about the project and its activities, events, deliverables and services, and constitutes an important source of information for our stakeholder communities. Apart from directly hosting a wealth of content, it also contains links to relevant information available elsewhere such as publications, presentations, etc. As such it offers stakeholder one-stop access to information about the project's background, ambition and results.

The project website was officially launched in June 2015. It has since been continuously updated with new content. Section 4.1.1 provides an overview of the content that we have produced, whereas section 4.1.2 analyses the usage of the site across the first two years.

4.1.1 Content

During the first twenty four months of PARTHENOS, we published 96 news items on the website, which were also disseminated via Twitter and our mailing list.

In general, the 96 unique news items published are divided as follow:

- 61 items in the category *News*
- 21 items in the category *Partners' news*
- 28 items in the category *Announcements*

Please note that the for some articles more than one category was applied, thus the discrepancy between the single news items and the categorized news items.

We are satisfied with our content production both quantitatively and qualitatively. On average we have produced around one high-quality article per week, thus keeping the website updated, informative and attractive for visitors.

In addition to publishing news items on PARTHENOS and its wider network on the website, WP8 has also been very active in facilitating the online publication of PARTHENOS products produced in other WPs; most notably the training modules developed by WP7 which were launched on a dedicated sub-site (<http://training.parthenos-project.eu>) in February 2017. It should be noted that the visitor analytics presented below only concern the main PARTHENOS site (<http://www.parthenos-project.eu>) and exclude visits to the training site.

The re-categorization of website content and the user experience overhaul which we undertook during M9 (described in detailed in the *First Year Communication Report*) has proven to be beneficial in the long term: the new browsing experience, loading time and the generally improved user experience have increased the attractiveness and effectiveness of the site; a finding that is confirmed by the website analytics data outlined below.

4.1.2 Analytics

We have carefully monitored usage of the website via Google Analytics. The analysis below covers the first twenty four months of the project (May 2015-April 2017). It should be noted that our analytics includes a weekly updated custom filter developed by WP8 to rule out spam/referral/ghost traffic, and the usage reported here therefore excludes traffic that would artificially inflate usage metrics.

Overall, the PARTHENOS website attracted 8,507 users in the first twenty four months of project; see Figure 2 for the development of user numbers since the launch of the site. This is marginally lower than we had anticipated, as the relevant target for website users as defined in the *First Year Communication Report* is 9,000 (see Section 5 for details). The other two defined indicators (Number of EU/EEA countries reached; total number of referrals) were met or exceeded. While the user numbers during year two are slightly below target, we do not believe that they are indicative of a general negative trend. Given that we far exceeded expectations in terms of website users in year one of the project which led to

the formulation of an ambitious target for year two, and given that most of the substantive results and services of PARTHENOS are yet to be released, it is unsurprising that the last twelve month were challenging in regard to increasing website traffic. We are, however, confident that we can substantially increase visitor numbers in the next reporting period. Indeed, the figures for March and June 2017 already indicate an upward trend, and with a clear strategy in place to disseminate PARTHENOS' results and services as they become available, we will be able to steadily increase website traffic over the next twelve months.

Figure 2: Website general overview

Furthermore, other website performance indicators continue to be encouraging. Regarding user engagement and retention, all key metrics (page views, pages-per-session, the average session duration and the bounce rate⁴) generally follow the same pattern as identified in the previous reporting period.

The page/session ratio (Figure 3) shows that the website netted an average of 2.31 pages per visit in its first twenty four months. The average session duration (Figure 4) is around 2 minutes, on par with the results recorded in the previous reporting period, as is the bounce rate which stands at around 60% over the two year period (Figure 5). This confirms the results presented in the *Initial Communication Plan* and the *First Year Communication Report*: PARTHENOS manages to create a high degree of user engagement and retention.

⁴ For a quick reference about terms used refer to <https://www.lovesdata.com/blog/google-analytics-glossary>

Figure 3: Pages/sessions

Figure 4: Average Session Duration

Figure 5: Bounce Rate

In terms of page views, the main catalyst of traffic is the website’s home page, as shown in Figure 6. In terms of content, all the ten most visited pages on the website are about the project’s description (/consortium, /about-the-project, /the-approach, /activities-and-wps, /news etc.). It should be noted, however, that Figure 6 reports only on content categorized as “pages”, and, therefore, does not encompass individual news items that are categorized by the CMS as separate objects (“posts”).

Figure 6: Page views

The search engine optimization strategies and the backend tweaks put in place since M12 (see *First Year Communication Report* for details) coupled with the increased profile of the project, has decreased the site's dependency on direct access (e.g. visitors typing the relevant URL directly into their browser) that characterised user acquisition during the first twelve months. As shown in Figure 8, when comparing M1-M12 with M13-24 we can detect a significant growth of (+47%) of visits through organic search, while direct access declined by 38%.

Figure 7: Acquisition channels M1-M24

While these changes in user acquisition were anticipated, a decline in referral traffic by 11% is less welcome news. To reverse this decline we will attempt to engage the project’s partners and third parties to refer more often to our website over the forthcoming period.

Figure 8: Acquisition channels - comparison (M1-M12 vs. M13-M24)

The search engines’ queries⁵ that generated clicks on the website are shown in Figure 9.

⁵ Given the current limit of Search Console, which renders organic queries for a period of maximum 90 days, Figure 9 shows only the data recorded in the period 01/03/2017 – 30/06/2017.

Query	Clicks
1 parthenos ↗	184 >>
2 parthenos project ↗	63 >>
3 initial communication ↗	7 >>
4 cnr ↗	5 >>
5 laurent romary ↗	4 >>
6 national research council italy ↗	4 >>
7 lrec 2018 ↗	4 >>
8 italian national research council ↗	4 >>
9 digital humanities summer school 2017 ↗	3 >>

Figure 9: Organic search queries

The average session duration and average pages per session ratio prove that the site performs generally well in terms of user retention. The engagement funnel is shown in Figure 10. As expected, the biggest drop-off of users occurs at the very beginning of the browsing experience. It should be noted that we managed to convert 1/3th of all sessions into further actions (clicks), leading to a lower drop-off rate. This trend closely follows the one identified in the previous reporting period.

Figure 10: User funnel

As shown in Figure 11, the referral traffic comes mostly from Twitter (through its “t.co” referral service), project partners’ websites and from the newsletter (**.campaign-archive2.com domains).

	NOReferral	3,737 % of Total: 20.99% (17,806)	57.37% Avg for View: 68.76% (-16.57%)	2,144 % of Total: 17.51% (12,244)
<input type="checkbox"/>	1. t.co	1,134 (30.35%)	38.27%	434 (20.24%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2. humanum.hypotheses.org	145 (3.88%)	81.38%	118 (5.50%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	3. huma-num.fr	120 (3.21%)	70.83%	85 (3.96%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	4. us11.campaign-archive2.com	111 (2.97%)	14.41%	16 (0.75%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	5. images.google.fr	98 (2.62%)	76.53%	75 (3.50%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	6. twitter.com	91 (2.44%)	1.10%	1 (0.05%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	7. oeaw.ac.at	86 (2.30%)	56.98%	49 (2.29%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	8. adf.ly	74 (1.98%)	100.00%	74 (3.45%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	9. dariah.eu	70 (1.87%)	57.14%	40 (1.87%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	10. facebook.com	57 (1.53%)	56.14%	32 (1.49%)

Figure 11: Referral sources

4.2 Social media

PARTHENOS understands the importance that social media currently have for communication purposes and carefully selects the most used and effective social networks to support its dissemination activities. We thereby take full advantage of the extensive social networks that are already in existence within the consortium.

Twitter remains central to our social media strategy. A PARTHENOS twitter account (@PARTHENOS_EU) was setup in month one of the project, and has been widely used to report on the project's activities, and alert followers to new content on the website.

Over the last twelve months we have produced ninety six distinct tweets that have been seen by a steadily increasing group of followers. By 30 April 2017, @PARTHENOS_EU was followed by 446 twitter users, and, over the period May 2016 to April 2017, our tweets have achieved an average monthly number of tweet impressions of 5,519. This means that while we more than doubled our number of followers, our impressions remained more or less the same as the year before. This is most likely caused by the fact that our number of tweets was lower (96 distinct tweets against 134 last period).

Figure 12: No of tweets and tweet impressions

Figure 13: No of Twitter followers

During this second year, we struggled to source news from within the project, which is reflected in the relatively low number of original tweets. To compensate we had to rely considerably on re-tweeting. The encouraging growth of our twitter following demonstrates

that this strategy has worked well during a period in the project’s lifetime when initial enthusiasm about the new project has subsided while many of its substantive results were still work-in-progress. With PARTHENOS now entering a phase when its results and services successively become available, and with a corresponding stepping up of dissemination activities foreseen, we are confident that we can maintain the positive trend in terms of followers, and significantly increase the numbers for tweets and tweet impressions over the next twelve months.

Twitter analytics provides an overview of the groups we are predominately reaching.

Figure 14: Twitter followers' interests

Not surprisingly, the main interest of our followers lies in science news, which demonstrates that we are reaching the right audience with our Twitter activities. The gender balance is almost equal.

Our other social media channels, YouTube, Flickr and Slideshare, have been sustained. They were primarily used for the dissemination of outcomes of other WPs. Especially the training WP has been very active and added many videos and presentations. 3 videos have been posted on the PARTHENOS' YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKJnFo_IFfoAl3VH51t1hw), with views ranging from 49 to 143. Furthermore, a total of 15 presentations were added to our Slideshare account (<https://www.slideshare.net/Parthenos>), with several presentations attracting more than 200 views.

4.3 Mailing list and newsletter

On 30 April 2016 the PARTHENOS mailing list comprised 162 subscribers. A year later this number had slowly but steadily risen to 192, and the M24 target of 200 subscribers was reached after the publication of the May 2017 newsletter.

The average opening rate is 38.9% and the click rate stands at 8.1%. Although this constitutes a decline in comparison to the previous period (see Figure 15), it should be noted that our initial opening rate of 56.2% was unsustainably high. Overall, the mailing list keeps on growing at an acceptable rate, while the engagement levels remain solid.

Figure 15: Mailing list opening and click rate (2015-2017)

Three newsletters were sent to the mailing list during the reporting period (July 2016, November 2016 and February 2017). Again the lack of high-quality project internal news prevented us from issuing additional newsletters. The newsletters focused on the announcement and reviews of big events (General Assembly, DH Summer School in Leipzig, the 3D workshop in Bordeaux, the joint ARIADNE-PARTHENOS workshop in Prato), as well as the launch of the training site in February 2017.

PARTHENOS

Building A Virtual, Resources and Tools
for Heritage Research Networking,
Aggregation and Synthesis

Newsletter Issue no. 7 - February 2017

PARTHENOS Training Launches Today!

PARTHENOS is today pleased to launch the [PARTHENOS Training Suite](#), a collection of materials to support training in Digital Research Infrastructures. The Training Suite, available online at training.parthenos-project.eu builds on existing knowledge within the cluster of partners in the PARTHENOS project. The materials included in the suite are not intended to replicate digital humanities (DH) skills training offered in formal and informal outlets elsewhere, but instead to expose some of the unique knowledge generated within research infrastructures. The intended audience for these materials is broad, including DH trainers looking to incorporate a greater awareness of infrastructure into their own teaching; self-learners from the research, cultural heritage or development communities curious about the context of work in an infrastructure; infrastructure-based researchers and professionals looking to deepen their understanding of their work context; through to policy makers and institutional leaders wanting to make more informed decisions about supporting access to research infrastructure.

[To the Training Website](#)

News you may be interested in

Digital 3D Objects in Art

Impressions from

The Network behind

Figure 16: PARTHENOS Newsletter February 2017

4.4 Publicity materials

During the reporting period, WP8 concentrated on distributing publicity materials developed during the project's first twelve month as well as creating new materials as and when required.

In terms of our existing materials, the PARTHENOS' poster proved very successful at various events. We therefore decided to produce two versions of this poster printed on fabric to facilitate a more professional presentation of PARTHENOS. We further continued to distribute the PARTHENOS flyer via our partners networks and at events.

For the workshop "Digital 3D Objects in Art and Humanities: Challenges of Creation, Interoperability and Preservation" (Bordeaux, November 2016), we designed a PARTHENOS' banner and produced PARTHENOS branded USB sticks which were distributed as hand-outs to delegates.

WP8 finally assists other PARTHENOS WPs to create publicity materials dedicated to their work. Together with WP7, a leaflet targeted at policymakers was produced that explains why the humanities need research infrastructures. WP8 was consulted on the content, design and distribution. The leaflets were disseminated through the partners and at events.

4.5 Events

WP8 is responsible for coordinating an appropriate PARTHENOS presence at relevant external events, as well as for organising a series of joint events over the course of the project.

4.5.1 External events

Presentations at and participation in relevant events such as conferences and workshops is an important way to disseminate our information and to get in contact with our target audiences. In order to keep track of events that we intend to target or had presence, we maintained two Basecamp calendars and populated these with details of such events.

These calendars are:

- External events to target

(https://basecamp.com/2932505/calendars/1476303/calendar_events): identified relevant events with no confirmed PARTHENOS presence .

- External events with PARTHENOS presence

(https://basecamp.com/2932505/calendars/1476304/calendar_events): identified relevant events where PARTHENOS has a confirmed presence.

In addition, a google spreadsheet is used to register PARTHENOS' presence at past events (see <http://tinyurl.com/juoau93>) .

In the second year, PARTHENOS partners participated at the following events to disseminate information about the project:

Date	Event	Action	Link	Audience
12 May 2016	EUDAT / CLARIN Community Meeting, Utrecht	Presenting Parthenos for CLARIN and EUDAT	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2016/centre-meeting	ca. 30
23-28 May 2016	LREC 2016	Dissemination of Parthenos and distribution of Parthenos Flyers at the CLARIN Booth	http://lrec2016.lrec-conf.org	
27-29 May 2016	Workshop of Cluster II- Innovation of the German Archaeological Institute: Military Innovations in Prehistory and Antiquity and the Military History of the Iberian Peninsula (Torres Vedras, Portugal)	Distribution of PARTHENOS flyers		ca. 20
13 June 2016	Workshop: Introduction to the Theory and Practice of Digital Humanities	PARTHENOS was highlighted during the workshop presentation and flyers were made available		ca. 20
13 June 2016	Open Repositories 2016	Distribution of PARTHENOS flyers	http://www.dri.ie/open-repositories-2016	ca. 200
28 June-1 July 2016	ITN DCH Summer School	Presenting Parthenos Strategy/Method/Infrastructure		ca.20
29 June 2016	Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER) Annual Conference, Helsinki	Presentation of WP7	http://libereurope.eu/annual-conference/	ca. 200
3-9 July 2016	ICOM 2016	Presenting Parthenos Strategy/Method/Infrastructure	http://network.icom.museum/icom-milan-2016//	ca.50
10-17 July 2016	15th IUVESTA School - Lasers for the Nano-Engineering of Surfaces Intl. School on Lasers in Materials Science - SLIMS, Venice	Distribution of Parthenos Flyers	http://www.slims.polimi.it/index.htm	ca. 60
11-16 July 2016	DH 2016	Dissemination of Parthenos and distribution of Parthenos Flyers at the CLARIN Booth	http://dh2016.adho.org	

Date	Event	Action	Link	Audience
12-15 July 2016	1st IPERION-CH Doctoral Summer School. Advanced characterization techniques, diagnostic tools & evaluation methods in heritage science	Distribution of PARTHENOS flyers	http://www.iperionch.eu/1st-iperion-ch-doctoral-summer-school-advanced-characterization-techniques-diagnostic-tools-evaluation-methods-in-heritage-science	ca. 50
1-4 Sep 2016	CIDOC CRM SIG Meeting	Presentation of info on work of Parthenos		ca.15
7-9 Sep 2016	V Convegno annuale AIUCD	Distribution of Parthenos Flyers	http://www.aiucd2016.unive.it/	
20-23 Sep 2016	11th Conference on Lasers in the Conservation of Artworks, Krakow	Distribution of Parthenos Flyers	http://lacona11.org/	ca. 100
10-13 Oct 2016	Humanum Meetups	Presenting 3M Tool, Parthenos Strategy for Data Mapping and Semantic Network		ca. 100
9-12 Nov 2016	Salone dell'Arte e del Restauro di Firenze	Poster presentation and distribution of Parthenos Flyers	http://www.salonerestaurofirenze.com/restauro/2016/en/	ca. 500
15-17 Nov 2016	Mapping Workshop with Symoghi Team	Presenting Parthenos Strategy/Method/Infrastructure		ca.5
7-8 Mar 2017	Illumination of Material Culture: a Symposium on Computations Photography and RTI	Invited keynote speech, title "Visualization: from desktop to the web?"	http://culturalheritageimaging.org/What_We_Do/Projects/neh-training/symposium/index.html	ca. 120
17 Mar 2017	Thesaurus building – Introducing THEMAS, a tool for multilingual thesaurus building	Distribution of Parthenos Flyers	http://calenda.org/392641 http://www.academyofathens.gr/el/node/1685	ca. 25

Table 1: Presence at external events

4.5.2 Joint events

During the second year, PARTHENOS organised three joint events as follows:

4.5.2.1 3D Workshop at Bordeaux, France - November 30th to December 2nd, 2016

Figure 17: Open Discussion session on the description of linked data and “historical metadata” in 3D modelling with Nicola Carboni, CNRS, MAP lab, France and George Bruseker, FORTH, Greece.

A workshop was jointly organized by CNR (Italy), CNRS (France) and Inria (France) within in the scope of Work Package 4 on Standardization, with support from the technical partners on behalf of the PARTHENOS Research Infrastructure. This was held in Bordeaux (France), from November 30th to December 2nd, 2016, and entitled "Digital 3D objects in Art and Humanities: challenges of creation, interoperability and preservation". The workshop was attended by selected PARTHENOS partners as well as some external experts, representative of both the technological and humanities domains. It aimed at enriching technical knowledge about 3D models, standards and tools in the PARTHENOS framework, addressing the common issues and epistemological questions related to the creation, use, reuse and preservation of 3D models. The discussion and feedback from this workshop is now available as a White Paper which can be downloaded from the PARTHENOS website (<http://www.parthenos-project.eu/parthenos-white-paper-digital-3d-objects-in-art-and-humanities-published/>). The White Paper also contains the full agenda and biographies of all the speakers.

4.5.2.2 Joint PARTHENOS-ARIADNE Workshop, Prato, Italy - 14th December 2016

Figure 18: Hella Hollander, WP3 Leader, presenting Common Policies for Implementation

ARIADNE held its Final Conference in Florence on the 15th and 16th December 2016 so the opportunity was taken to organise a joint workshop to introduce PARTHENOS and its objectives to the attendees of these events and preceding ARIADNE workshops (the last one being held Wednesday morning) in nearby Prato where PIN is located. The programme (see Appendix A for details) covered the main topics addressed in PARTHENOS and introduced the VRE and how this is going to be further developed. The workshop concluded with a demonstration of the ARIADNE Catalogue as the functionality of this would be similar to some of the services that PARTHENOS will provide. The workshop was very well attended (forty nine people) with everyone staying until the end despite the cold weather.

4.5.2.3 ESU Summer School for Researchers, Leipzig, 23rd-29th July 2016

Figure 19: Franco Niccolucci with WP7 Leader and lead trainer Jennifer Edmond and the five ESU students

The University of Leipzig hosts the annual European Summer School “Culture and Technology” which aims at bringing together young scholars from the Humanities, Engineering and Information Sciences. PARTHENOS was invited to present their first training module to five students from the US, Canada, Egypt and Russia who signed up to learn more about Research Infrastructures, how to access and use them and the related research agenda funded by the European Union which is encouraging the development of Research Infrastructures to support various different disciplines. The training also addressed the different perspectives, from researchers to managers and the modules are available on the PARTHENOS website at <http://training.parthenos-project.eu/training-modules/>.

4.6 Publications

As was expected, no peer-reviewed PARTHENOS-related publications were submitted during the second year of the project. However, the below provides an overview of non-peer reviewed items that were published:

- “DARIAH and PARTHENOS: Advancing Digital Cultural Heritage Research Together”, in DARIAH Newsletter and DARIAH Update, July 2016
- “Workshop ‘Introducing PARTHENOS – Integrating the Digital Humanities’”, in CLARIN Newsflash, October 2016
- “Premier atelier PARTHENOS (projet H2020) sur les objets 3D dans les humanités et les arts”, 14 November 2016, Huma Num blog, <https://humanum.hypotheses.org/2872>
- “Inria’s Alpage project team: historians and computer scientists unite in the European Parthenos project”, interview on Inria website, 5 December 2016, <https://www.inria.fr/en/centre/paris/news/inria-s-alpage-project-team-historians-and-computer-scientists-unite-in-the-european-parthenos-project>
- “Online leren met Parthenos”, DANS website, news item, 20 March 2017, <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/actueel/nieuws/online-leren-met-parthenos>
- “Mise en ligne des interviews du premier atelier PARTHENOS (objets 3D, patrimoine culturel et humanités numériques)”, Huma-Num blog, 24 April 2017, <https://humanum.hypotheses.org/3232>
- “PARTHENOS Training shows a new direction in training for Research Infrastructures”, DARIAH-CE blog, 25 April 2017, <https://dariahre.hypotheses.org/654>

4.7 Scientific communication

WP8 is tasked to analyse, support and improve scientific communication in the PARTHENOS target areas of language studies, digital humanities, digital heritage, archaeology and history. In particular, the WP8 Scientific Communication task aims to evaluate the creation of a scientific e-journal in the service of e-humanities research and the adoption and management of an Open Access repository for pre-print storage of scientific papers.

In the course of the second year we continued and finished the analysis and evaluation of existing relevant e-journals. The survey we conducted in T8.3 among PARTHENOS' partners into their use of e-journals focusing on Digital Humanities resulted in a good overview. Information on thirty nine journals was collected. The focus of a third of these journals was mostly inter- or trans-disciplinary, some specialized in specific time periods or geographical areas (especially in History and Archaeology), some had a more theoretical or technical focus on computational, methodological, and communicational aspects, while a last group concentrated on specific disciplines e.g. Archaeology or Linguistics. Open Access in one way or the other was very common (80% of all surveyed journals). Even though most journals appeared regularly (most commonly quarterly), for some publication was irregular or unclear. For more details see the table on surveyed e-journals in Annex B.

Overall our survey suggests that the existing e-journals largely fill the need of the field, although small gaps can be found. A new journal might close such a gap in a specialized field, but besides the considerable effort required to establish a new journal, there still remains the sustainability question: what will happen to a journal initiated by PARTHENOS after the end of the project? Therefore, we came to the conclusion that there is no immediate need to set up a new e-journal and that the task should focus on alternative ways to enhance scientific communication.

Being aware that the Humanities at Scale (HaS) project (<http://has.dariah.eu/>) is addressing similar questions, existing contacts were used and experiences were exchanged in the course of several meetings.⁶ Indeed, HaS shared our conclusion that to set up another e-journal would not solve the problem it is seeking to address: to raise awareness about digital humanities methods. Instead, HaS decided to set up a “meta blog” that (re)publishes all types of publications (blogs articles, grey literature, articles, etc.) chosen by an editorial board for their quality that deal with “methods in Digital Humanities”. The texts chosen for republication will be taken from different disciplines and languages. The goal is to trigger the community to describe methods in more detail and to encourage discussions about areas that are otherwise barely covered in the Digital Humanities literature.

Our chosen approach resembles the one of HaS, and we will continue the initiated collaboration in order to benefit from cross-fertilisation and to avoid duplication of effort.

⁶ PARTHENOS T8.3 meeting in The Hague (21 February 2017); PARTHENOS WP8 meeting Heraklion (17 May); HaS virtual meeting 13 June 2017.

Indeed, we are intending to setup a PARTHENOS Hub that shares some similarities to HaS' meta-blog. A lot of scientific communication nowadays takes place outside of established journals in blogs, discussion groups and other social media tools. To identify valuable content pertaining to a specific topic, not only from established journals but also from these other sources, and to select and appraise such content via an editorial board for (re)publishing is a promising idea to further scientific communication.

The PARTHENOS Hub will therefore provide an infrastructure enabling the re-publication of properly assessed information from different sources (repositories, blogs, scientific social media, etc.) pertaining to specific topics. It will be freely accessible, citable, reusable with clearly stated conditions. In the long run, retrieval and collection of information will be made automatic if possible. Additional services especially in connection with repositories will be considered. The Hub will be a place where one can access information and interact with it: it will enable users to discuss, share, improve and contribute relevant content.

We have started to collect ideas and possible solutions to realize the PARTHENOS Hub, addressing questions such as what infrastructure do we require? Where and how will we collect content? How will we involve the PARTHENOS communities? How will we connect to other existing infrastructures? How will we assure the quality of the content?

While detailed answers to many such questions are still work-in-progress, the general contour of our strategy has been established. In regard to infrastructure, we intend to re-use the solution currently being developed by HaS which is based on the Pressforward Wordpress plugin. Currently, we are investigating to what extent the HaS solution will cover our needs or whether additional effort from our side will be required. To ensure the quality of the content that will be published via the Hub, we have decided to develop a variety of thematic issues, with each issue having an editor (or a group of editors) with responsibility for content selection and quality assurance. The sources can be traditional articles, documents from repositories, blog entries and many more. To ensure accessibility to the content it will either be reachable by a persistent link to the open access document or (re)published in a way that it becomes citable.

Details concerning legal issues, technical aspects and cooperation with other partners including existing Open Access repositories will be dealt with in the forthcoming reporting period.

Parallel to the activities on e-journals and the PARTHENOS Hub, we continued to collect information on open access repositories and on existing relevant initiatives such as the general approach provided by OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>), including the services of ZENODO (<http://zenodo.org>). This was not our main focus in the second year, however, as we realised very early on that it would be advantageous to connect the PARTHENOS Hub with an open access repository. Hence, we decided to first collect requirements in regard to linking the Hub to a specific repository. We will use these requirements in a second step as specifications for the selection of a specific open access repository for adoption and management by PARTHENOS.

In summary, the outcomes of our activities in the second year are:

- an evaluation of relevant e-journals
- a decision not to set up a new e-journal, but to pursue an alternative way of scientific communication via the PARTHENOS Hub
- a first draft for the PARTHENOS Hub
- a close cooperation with the HaS project

5 Summary evaluation of activities during the second year

Table 2 offers a summary evaluation of our activities reported in detail above against the performance targets set in the *First Year Communication Report*.

Indicator	Cumulative target M1-M24⁷	Actual M1-M24
Total number of website visitors	9,000	8,507
Number of EU/EEA countries reached through website	31	31
Total number of referrals	2,200	3,737
Number of contacts in the mailing list	200	192
Number of twitter followers	400	446
Avg. monthly number of tweet impressions	8,000	5,519
Number of joint events	1-2	3
Avg. number of attendees at joint events	30	ca. 30
Number of leaflets/other publicity materials distributed (to partners)	4,500	ca. 4,500
Number of presentations/posters at conferences, workshops, etc.	18-20	At least 22
Number of attendees reached at conferences	700	> 1,000
Number of scientific papers	0-1	0
Articles in professional journals and online newsletters	18	> 20

Table 2: Evaluation against targets

As can be seen we have reached, and in many cases significantly exceeded, most of our performance targets. The three exceptions pertain to total number of website visitors; number of contacts in the mailing list and avg. monthly number of tweet impressions. While the figures for these indicators are less than expected, we do not believe that they are indicative of a substantial, long-term problem. As explained in more detail in sections 4.1 and 4.2 above, the relatively low figures are explainable by the fact that the last year was slow in regard to PARTHENOS-related news, which was in large parts caused by the stage

⁷ Please note that in some instance there is a discrepancy between the targets for M24 as presented here and in Table 6 of the *First Year Communication Report*. This is due to the fact that in the First Year Communication Report some targets were implicitly expressed as only covering the present reporting period (i.e. M13-24) while others were cumulative covering the period M1-M24. In order to avoid confusion, we have decided to express all targets as cumulative, and have accordingly re-calculated the following indicator: Total number of website visitors; total number of referrals; number of leaflets distributed; number of posters/presentations at conferences, workshops, etc.; number of attendees reached at conferences; Articles in professional journals and newsletters.

we have reached in the project's lifecycle: i.e. we experienced a relative lull after the initial enthusiasm about the new project and before an anticipated forthcoming surge in interest when PARTHENOS' substantive results will go online. With more and more results becoming available over the next twelve months, we are confident that we can significantly raise our performance in regard to those three indicators over the next period. It should further be noted that we only marginally missed our targets in regard to total number of website visitors and number of contacts in the mailing list, with the average number of monthly tweet impressions the only indicator that was missed by a significant amount. Given that our Twitter following has increased above target during the reporting period, we suspect that we set the target for tweet impressions unreasonably high for the last period, and a more realistic growth rate for tweet impressions has been set for the forthcoming period (see section 7 for details).

6 Planning of activities for third year

6.1 Website

Year three will be a pivotal year for PARTHENOS, and we expect the website to accelerate its evolution from a dissemination and communication tool to a platform hosting not only news and documents, but also resources, tools and repositories that will be developed by the project in the second half of its lifespan.

This shift has already started with the integration of the Training Modules, accessible via the subdomain <http://training.parthenos-project.eu>, which helped WP8 to test the processes and the technical solutions necessary to successfully host different kind of contents on its platform. The site's Content Management System (CMS), despite its signature modularity, needs in fact several optimization and under-the-hood tweaks to perform acceptably for the project's future needs. This is the reason why for the next period our website related activities will be devoted primarily to two important areas: website scalability and content creation and management.

The need of the former was already explained in the previous paragraphs, while the latter will mostly (but not only) focus on the areas of improvement identified in this document. In terms of content, the aim is to moderately increase the current level of content production quantitatively, and to focus more decidedly on high-quality news and results from within the PARTHENOS project, while also improving referrals to our content (mainly through partners' website and platforms already in place).

6.2 Social media

In regard to our existing social media channels, the priority for the next twelve month is to significantly increase the number of tweets we issue as well as to improve their reach (tweet impressions). This will also enable us to continually increase the number of followers to the PARTHENOS Twitter account. To achieve these goals, it will be crucial to increase the number of original tweets relating to PARTHENOS events, results and services, thereby lessening our reliance on re-tweeting. Given that it is anticipated that the rate by which

PARTHENOS' achievements and services will become available will accelerate significantly over the next twelve months, such an expansion of our Twitter activities is realistic.

Apart from sustaining and expanding our existing social media channels, we will further create a PARTHENOS presence of Facebook. While we initially had some reservations about using Facebook as a medium to engage a predominately scientific audience, the experience of related projects shows that Facebook can be used as a very effective dissemination channel, and several PARTHENOS' partners already have a presence on the platform. Facebook also has the potential to reach a slightly different, more general audience. The interactive nature of Facebook, finally, makes it an effective tool for enhancing community engagement.

6.3 Mailing list and newsletters

For the coming year, we expect to continue the steady growth of our mailing list. In particular, we are planning to contact the network of international projects and initiatives identified in WP8's International Liaison task to solicit further high-quality subscriptions to our email list. This effort together with the anticipated general expansion of our dissemination activities should lead to a significant increase in the size of our mailing list.

The newsletter has proved itself a valuable instrument to reach a relatively small, but highly engaged group. Our aim continues to be to send three to four full newsletters per year. Additional shorter and more focused mailshots may be sent out as and when required.

6.4 Publicity materials

We are aiming to translate the general PARTHENOS flyer into a variety of languages, in order to extend PARTHENOS' reach in those regions where English does not act as a lingua franca among our target audiences. This process is already underway, and translations into Italian, Polish and German are currently in progress.

Furthermore, updated versions of the PARTHENOS poster and flyer will be produced. The updated versions will focus more on PARTHENOS emerging results and services rather than on the project's background and context. We will further co-ordinate and provide assistance to other WPs that aim to produce their own dedicated PR materials, as well as help with the dissemination of such WP-specific materials as is currently the case with the Why Standards? leaflet produced by WP4.

Both WPs7 and 8 are currently working on several short video interviews. There already exists close contact between the two teams to coordinate this activity, and we will continue and deepen the collaboration over the next twelve months. Audio-visual material has in our own experience great potential to reach bigger and younger audiences than is possible via more traditional text-based information.

6.5 Events

6.5.1 External events

The Basecamp calendars mentioned in section 4.5.1 above will continue to be maintained and updated, and periodic reminders will be sent to partners to encourage them to disseminate information about PARTHENOS at events they are attending. All partners will be notified of calls for papers considered to be relevant to PARTHENOS, and invited to submit posters, papers and similar. Many partners are already active within their own domains with regards to participation at workshops and conference.

6.5.2 Joint events

We will continue our joint-events programme in year three, and plan future workshops in consultation with the other related Humanities RIs. Two that have been confirmed for year three are:

- 1) The FAIR Principles with ERIHS in Iraklion, Crete on the 16th May 2017.
- 2) Applying the FAIR principles – Utrecht, Netherlands on the 6th July 2017 (following the DH2017 Benelux Conference) which is being held in conjunction with CLARIN and DARIAH.

CLARIN has also invited PARTHENOS to attend its annual conference which is on the 18th-20th September 2017 in Budapest, Hungary. This will provide a good opportunity to promote the project to Eastern European attendees as recommended by the Mid-term Review.

Other possibilities currently under discussion for year three are a follow-up workshop on 3D data, following publication of the White Paper “Digital 3D Objects in the Art and Humanities: challenges of creation, interoperability and preservation” in early 2018; a joint event with EHRI and also some training events. Looking forward even further, current proposals for year four include:

- Training Workshops (i.e. organised through WP7)
- Panel of experts at M45 – this is an event involving the external experts who have participated in reviewing the PARTHENOS WP3 outputs as part of WP2 during Year 3.
- Final Event M46/7
- Another joint workshop with CLARIN, possibly at their annual conference (September 2018)
- A joint event with DARIAH.

A further possibility is a joint workshop between PARTHENOS and the Social Science ERICs concerning the PARTHENOS Data Management Plan as there appears to be considerable common interest.

6.6 Publications

We expect that most substantive, peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to PARTHENOS will be published towards the end of the project. We envisage that a maximum of one to two such publications will be published or be in-press by the end of the forthcoming reporting period. In the meantime, we intend to keep on publishing smaller articles and news items that focus on the project’s preliminary results.

6.7 Scientific communication

In the third year we will continue to develop the PARTHENOS Hub as a new way of scientific communication. We will elaborate and further develop the outline of the PARTHENOS Hub. In particular we will look at the needed infrastructure in order to release a first working prototype with all basic features by the end of the third year. The results, first evaluations, and possible necessary adjustments will be fully documented.

We will publish a first thematic issue on the Hub as an example and a test-bed. It is anticipated that this first issue will be based on the work of a PARTHENOS WP. In parallel, we will approach possible partners from other projects and infrastructures for a second issue.

We will further address open questions regarding e.g. legal issues and provide information and guidelines for users so that they can quickly ascertain the possibilities of the Hub. Furthermore, we will investigate what additional features may be needed by involving the PARTHENOS communities and other partners.

Regarding the adoption and management of a scientific repository service for open access pre-print storage of scientific papers, we will continue our investigation which will result in the selection of an appropriate existing repository. We aim to closely connect our work on the repository to the PARTHENOS Hub.

7 Evaluation criteria for year 3

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Cumulative target (M1-36)</i>
Total number of website visitors	13,500
Number of EU/EEA countries reached through website	31
Total number of referrals	5,800
Number of contacts in the mailing list	220
Number of twitter followers	520
Avg. monthly number of tweet impressions	6,000
Number of joint events	5-6
Avg. number of attendees at joint events	30
Number of leaflets/other publicity materials distributed (to partners)	4,750
Number of presentations/posters at conferences, workshops, etc.	>30
Number of attendees reached at conferences	>1,400
Number of scientific papers	0-2
Articles in professional journals and online newsletters	25

Table 3: Evaluation criteria Year 3

Appendix A: Programme joint event Introducing PARTHENOS – integrating the digital humanities

Wednesday 14th December 14:00 - 17:30 – PIN, Italy

AGENDA

14:00 Welcome and overview – *Franco*

What PARTHENOS aims to achieve, the tools and services it will offer to researchers.

14:20 The main user requirements identified as key aspects of PARTHENOS – *Sebastian Drude, CLARIN*. The PARTHENOS Services are based on a thorough analysis of the requirements coming from Use cases contributed by the PARTHENOS communities.

14:40 a. Common policies – *Hella Hollander, KNAW-DANS*

Common policies are key to enabling effective collaboration and cross-discipline research in the humanities. PARTHENOS is implementing an online wizard to support researchers, policy makers and data managers to identify, select and implement the relevant policies for their work.

15:00 b. Standardisation (SSK) – *Laurent Romary, INRIA*

The Standards Survival Kit has been designed to support humanities researchers based upon over 24 Use Cases. It consist of an online tool designed to teach researchers to use standards, answer their questions and guide them and provide them with information on standards.

15:20 c. Services to be provided – *Carlo Meghini, CNR*

The architects of the PARTHENOS infrastructure have designed a set of services, which can be divided into two broad categories: services providing cross-community functionality, such as dataset or service discovery; and services providing domain specific functionality, such as text mining, shared through the infrastructure for use by all communities. The presentation will overview the PARTHENOS architecture and will briefly present both categories of services.

15:40 d. Training – *Jennifer Edmond, TCD*

Infrastructure projects commonly provide training materials to support users looking to adapt the tools and resources the project has developed and maintains. The PARTHENOS project will be developing resources of this sort, but also taking the idea of providing training in a research infrastructure a step further by addressing some of the key knowledge gaps in the wider community, such as a lack of awareness of what research infrastructures are and do, how they are created and maintained, and how the scale of their operations creates unique opportunities, challenges and knowledge.

16:00 Coffee break

16:20 Brief overview of the technologies used to achieve this – *Carlo Meghini, CNR*

PARTHENOS will be implemented on top of a very solid technological architecture, the gCube suite, currently powering the D4Science infrastructure. This presentation will review the main design principles of the architecture and will touch upon the most important components.

16:40 Demonstration of common services in ARIADNE which are similar to those to be offered by PARTHENOS - *Achille Felicetti, PIN*.

17:00 How to become involved in PARTHENOS – *Franco Niccolucci, PIN*

- Questions and answers session - *Round table*
- Summary of discussion, round up.

Appendix B: Surveyed e-journals

N.	Name of journal	Link (URL)	Description of Journal	Language	Peer review	Appears	Open Access
1	Applied Physics A Materials Science & Processing	http://link.springer.com/journal/339	Applied Physics A publishes experimental and theoretical investigations in applied physics and material science as regular articles, rapid communications, and invited papers. The journal has an interdisciplinary approach.	English	Yes	Monthly	Partly (hybrid)
2	Archeologia e Calcolatori	http://soi.cnr.it/archaeology/	Archeologia e Calcolatori is an open access international scholarly Journal devoted to theoretical and methodological aspects of computing and information technology applied to archaeology	Multilingual: German, Spanish, Italian, French, English	Yes	Yearly	Yes
3	DH Commons	http://dhcommons.org/	"DHCommons, an initiative of centerNet, is an online hub focused on matching digital humanities projects seeking assistance with scholars interested in project collaboration." (http://dhcommons.org/about)	English, multilingual	Yes	1st Issue July 2015	Yes
4	Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage	http://www.journals.elsevier.com/digital-application-s-in-archaeology-and-cultural-heritage	Devoted to the publication of 3D digital models of the world's cultural heritage sites, monuments, and palaeoanthropological remains accompanied by associated academic articles	English	Yes	Quarterly	Partly (hybrid)
5	Digital Classics online	http://journals.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/index.php/dco	It covers topics from classical and ancient studies and related fields in relation to application and development of methods in digital humanities.	German, English, French, Italian		unclear (started 2015)	Yes
6	Digital Humanities Quarterly	http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/	ADHO-published, open-access, digital journal covering all aspects of digital media in the humanities	English, German, Italian, French	Yes	quarterly	Yes
7	Digital Literary Studies	https://journals.psu.edu/dls	Open-access, covering those aspects of Digital Humanities primarily concerned with computational approaches to literary analysis/criticism, or critical/literary approaches to electronic literature, digital media, and textual resources.	English	Yes		Yes
8	Digital Medievalist Journal	https://journal.digitalmedievalist.org/	Digital Medievalist is an international web-based community for medievalists working with digital media. It was established in 2003 to help scholars meet the increasingly sophisticated demands faced by designers of contemporary digital projects. Digital Medievalist publishes an open access journal, sponsors conference sessions, runs an email discussion list and encourages best practice in digital medieval resource creation.	English	Yes		Yes

N.	Name of journal	Link (URL)	Description of Journal	Language	Peer review	Appears	Open Access
9	Digital Scholarship in the Humanities	http://dsh.oxfordjournals.org/	Formerly LLC, Oxford journal, high profile	english	yes		unsure
10	Digital Studies / Le champ numérique	http://www.digitalstudies.org/	published by the Société canadienne des humanités numériques (CSDH/SCHN), a partner in ADHO, (cf. http://digitalhumanities.berkeley.edu/resources/digital-humanities-journals)	English, French, other languages (i.e. Polish) and their respective translation are both published	Yes	publishes articles and issues on a rolling basis, with volumes for each calendar year	Yes. Golden Open Access
11	Digitalia	http://digitalia.sbn.it/	Digitalia, the journal of digitalities in cultural heritage lies within the field of the specialized serial editing in Italy; its first goal is the study and the critical debate on topics relating to the application of digital technologies to various typologies of cultural heritage	Italian	No	6 monthly	Yes
12	DSH: Digital Scholarship in the Humanities	http://dsh.oxfordjournals.org/	published by Oxford Journals on behalf of EADH and ADHO. "international, peer reviewed journal which publishes original contributions on all aspects of digital scholarship in the Humanities including, but not limited to, the field of what is currently called the Digital Humanities. Long and short papers report on theoretical, methodological, experimental, and applied research and include results of research projects, descriptions and evaluations of tools, techniques, and methodologies, and reports on work in progress. DSH also publishes reviews of books and resources." (http://dsh.oxfordjournals.org/about)	English	Yes	quarterly	No
13	GeoHumanities	http://www.tandfonline.com/loi/rqeo	Covers conceptual and methodological debates in geography and the humanities; critical reflections on analog and digital artistic productions; and new scholarly interactions occurring at the intersections of geography and multiple humanities disciplines.	English	Yes	6 monthly	Yes
14	Heritage Science	https://heritagesciencejournal.springeropen.com/	Dedicated to heritage science (analysis, study, restoration, etc.) including "Development and application of statistical methods and algorithms for data analysis to further understanding of culturally significant objects, publication of reference and corpus datasets as supplementary information to the statistical and analytical studies above"	English	Yes	Irregular	Yes
15	Humanities	http://www.mdpi.com/journal/humanities	Scholarly papers across all humanities disciplines	English	Yes	3 monthly	Yes
16	International Journal of Digital Curation	http://www.ijdc.net/	Online journal, publishes twice a year in digital curation, research data management and related issues.	English	Yes		Yes

N.	Name of journal	Link (URL)	Description of Journal	Language	Peer review	Appears	Open Access
17	International Journal of Digital Libraries (IJDL)	http://link.springer.com/	This journal examines the theory and practice of acquisition, definition, organization, management, and dissemination of digital information via global networking.	English		4 issues a year	No
18	International Journal of Geographical Information Science	http://www.tandfonline.com/loi/tgis20#.V3_S BdSLTmG	International Journal of Geographical Information Science provides a forum for the exchange of original ideas, approaches, methods and experiences in the rapidly growing field of geographical information science (GIScience). It is (arguably) the journal of reference in GIS	English	Yes	Monthly	Partly (hybrid)
19	International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era	http://hde.sagepub.com/ ; http://www.digital-heritage-journal.eu/	The journal's main scope is to advance the theory, research, practice and to provide a bridge of communication for academicians, researchers, professionals, scientists and students worldwide working in the different areas and disciplines of Digital Heritage.	English	Yes	Quarterly	No
20	International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing	http://www.eupublishing.com/loi/ijhac	One of the world's premier multi-disciplinary, peer-reviewed forums for research on all aspects of arts and humanities computing.	English	Yes	2 issues a year	Partly (hybrid)
21	Internet Archaeology	http://intarh.ac.uk/	It publishes quality academic content and explores the potential of electronic publication through the inclusion of video, audio, searchable data sets, full-colour images, visualisations, animations and interactive mapping.	any language; summary in English, French, German, Italian or Spanish	Yes		Yes
22	Italian Journal of Computational Linguistics	http://www.aicli.it/index.php?slab=ri vista	Proceedings of the annual Conference of the "Associazione Italiana di Linguistica Computazionale", Special Issue in Dec. 2016 on <i>Digital Humanities and Computational Linguistics</i>	Italian, English	Yes	once a year + a Special Issue	Yes
23	Journal for Language Technology and Computational Linguistics	http://www.jlcl.org/index.php?modus=home&language=	focuses on original research papers and book reviews, issues may have a specific thematic focus. Published by the <i>German Society for Computational Linguistics & Language Technology</i> (GSCL).	German, English	Yes	twice a year (May, October)	Yes
24	Journal of Archaeological Science	http://www.journals.sevier.com/journal-of-archaeological-science/	"The Journal of Archaeological Science is aimed at archaeologists and scientists with particular interests in advancing the development and application of scientific techniques and methodologies to all areas of archaeology". It is (arguably) the journal of reference in Archaeometry/Archaeological Science, and strongly promotes the digital aspects of it	English	Yes	Monthly	No
25	Journal of Cultural Analytics	http://culturalanalytics.org/	Open-access, journal dedicated to the computational study of culture	English	Yes		Yes
26	Journal of Cultural Heritage (JCH)	http://www.journals.sevier.com/journal-of-cultural-heritage	"A Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology for Conservation and Awareness" It is (arguably) the journal of reference in Cultural Heritage, and promotes the digital aspects of it	English	Yes	Bimonthly	Partly (hybrid)

N.	Name of journal	Link (URL)	Description of Journal	Language	Peer review	Appears	Open Access
27	Journal of Digital Humanities	http://journalofdigitalhumanities.org/	Features scholarship, tools, and conversations produced, identified, and tracked by members of the digital humanities community through Digital Humanities Now	English	Yes	irregularly	Yes
28	Journal of Digital Media and Literacy	http://www.jodml.org/	traditional research articles alongside hybrid, mixed-media articles and creative digital projects, presents a variety of perspectives on the intersection between digital and media literacy, technology, culture, and civic engagement. The content is descriptive and prescriptive in regards to how scholars, activists, consumers, practitioners, and educators engage with all aspects of digital and media literacy throughout the communities in which they work, live, and serve.	English	Yes		
29	Journal of the Text Encoding Initiative	http://journal.tei-c.org/	"the official journal of the Text Encoding Initiative Consortium. It publishes selected papers from the annual TEI Conference and Members' Meeting and special issues based on topics or themes of interest to the community or in conjunction with special events or meetings associated with TEI." (http://journal.tei-c.org/)	English	Yes	regularly (at least once a year)	Yes
30	Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)	http://jocch.acm.org/	JOCCH publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in support of Cultural Heritage	English	Yes	quarterly-ish	No
31	Kairos: A Journal of Rhetoric, Technology, and Pedagogy	http://kairos.technorhetoric.net/	it examines digital and multimodal composing practices, promoting work that enacts its scholarly argument through rhetorical and innovative uses of new media.	English	refereed	2-3 issues a year	Yes
32	Les Cahiers du Numérique	https://lcn.revuesonline.com/accueil.jsp		French		4 issues a year	
33	Library Hi Tech	http://www.emeraldinsight.com/loi/ih	Library Hi Tech features articles which explore new tools for managing and giving access to information, innovative ways of understanding interactions with users in both digital and hybrid environments, and unconventional approaches to library and information environments.	English		4 issues a year	Partly (hybrid)
34	Parcours numériques	http://www.parcoursnumeriques-pum.ca/	Journal/books collection but also website	French (Canadian)			
35	Proceedings of SPIE Optics for Arts, Architecture, and Archaeology (O3A)	http://proceedings.spiedigitallibrary.org/volume.aspx?volumeid=17246	The papers included in these proceedings are part of the technical conference SPIE optical metrology conference devoted to methods of examination of heritage objects – O3A: Optics for Arts, Architecture and Archaeology – O3A. Advanced methodologies and new instruments for the study, documentation, safeguarding, preservation and conservation of the heritage are discussed.	English	Yes	Biyearly	Partly (hybrid)

N.	Name of journal	Link (URL)	Description of Journal	Language	Peer review	Appears	Open Access
36	Research Data Journal for the Humanities and Social Sciences	http://www.brill.com/products/online-resources/research-data-journal-humanities-and-social-sciences	Data journal. "Research Data Journal for the Humanities and Social Sciences (RDJ) is a peer reviewed e-only open access journal, which is designed to comprehensively document and publish deposited data sets and to facilitate their online exploration."	English, Dutch	Yes		Yes
37	Revue française en sciences de l'information et de la communication	https://rfsic.revues.org/1984		French			
38	Studies in Conservation	http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/yvic20/current	Studies in Conservation is an international peer-reviewed journal for the conservation of historic and artistic works. The intended readership includes the conservation professional in the broadest sense of the term: practising conservators of all types of object, conservation, heritage and museum scientists, collection or conservation managers, teachers and students of conservation, and academic researchers in the subject areas of arts, archaeology, the built heritage, materials history, art technological research and material culture.	English	Yes	Bimonthly	Partly (hybrid)
39	Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften	http://www.zfdg.de/	publishes research results in DH, on behalf of the <i>Forschungsverbund Marbach Weimar Wolfenbüttel</i> and <i>Digital Humanities in the German speaking area (DHd)</i> . Published on their own interface, new ways of publishing, access and sustainability.	German, English	Yes	publishes articles on a rolling basis on the website	Yes